

A STUDY ON LIBRARY USAGE PATTERN: SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE SELECTED COLLEGES

Dr. S. Selvendran

Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Angappa College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Selvendran, "A Study on Library Usage Pattern: Special Reference to the Selected Colleges", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 50-53, 2018.

Introduction:

Information is a vital and an indispensable component of any college environment. It makes for effectiveness in any college system. Both faculty and students need to use information daily in their various college endeavors. For decades, faculty and students have actively used the library and its resources as their main information source. Alemna, (2000) states that for centuries libraries have served as repositories of information and knowledge that have provided the vital underpinnings for socio- economic, political and cultural development in any civilization. Their relationship with cultural progress has been so interdependent that it is needless to argue whether man's cultural advancement merely produces libraries as by product.

Statement of the Problem:

College libraries are citadel of college excellence, established to facilitate learning, teaching research, scholarship and knowledge dissemination. Critical use of information resources is fundamental to higher education. Informed library users know that libraries have resources that are more comprehensive and scholarly than other sources such as the cyber. Students not well exposed to library resources may not be aware of resources a library have or how to make use of them. This, partly, may be because the faculty staff or library staff failed to inform them of the resources available in the library which in turn may affect the students' college works or performances.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To learn library services, resources and facilities used by the users.
- ✓ To know how satisfied are with available resources and services in the library.
- ✓ To suggest remedies that may help to the users.

Methodology of the Study:

Source of the Data:

The present study relies both on the primary and secondary data.

Sampling Size:

The study was conducted in selected colleges. As per the requirement of the study only 200 students selected as sample.

Sample Selection:

Convenient Sampling technique used by the researcher during sample section.

Tools and Technique Used:

- Percent Analysis: Percent analysis refers to a special kind of ratio, which is used in making comparison between two (or) more series of data.

$$\text{Formula} = \frac{\text{Number of Respondents}}{\text{Total number of Respondent}}$$

- Correlation: Karl Pearson co-efficient technique used to estimate the level of association among the variables.

Analysis and Interpretations:

Sample Respondents by Gender:

Table 1

S.No	Gender	Sample Size	%
1	Male	66	33
2	Female	134	67
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

67% of the sample respondents are females.

Sample Respondents by Age:

Table 2

S.No	Age	Sample Size	%
1	17	14	7
2	18	30	15
3	19	90	45
4	20	66	33

	Total	200	100
--	-------	-----	-----

Source: Primary Data

Majority 45% of the sample respondents are in the age of 19 years.

Sample Respondents by Course:

Table 3

S.No	Course	Sample Size	%
1	B.com	50	25
2	B.com CA	62	31
3	B.SC IT	30	15
4	B.com IT	6	3
5	B.Sc	28	14
6	B.A English	24	12
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

31% of the sample respondents are studying B.Com CA.

Sample Respondents by Orientation Class:

Table 4

S.No	Orientation Class	Sample Size	%
1	Yes	140	70
2	No	60	30
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Majority 70% of the sample respondents are able to get orientation class.

Sample Respondents by Visiting Time:

Table 5

S.No	Visiting Time	No. of Respondents	%
1	In class	6	3
2	During lunch	36	18
3	After college	48	24
4	During free hours	110	55
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

55% of the sample respondents are visiting library during free hours.

Sample Respondents by Major Section-Visit:

Table 5

S.No	Major Section- Visit	Sample Size	%
1	Circulation section	82	43
2	Reading section	90	48
3	Internet section	12	6
4	Others	6	3
	Total	190	100

Source: Primary Data

A majority 48 % of respondents felt that Reading section considered as a major section.

Sample Respondents by No of Sections Visit:

Table 6

S.No	Various Section- Visit	Sample Size	%
1	One	70	35
2	Two or more	130	65
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Majority 65 % of respondents are going to two or more sections per visit.

Sample Respondents by Time Spend Sections:

Table 7

S.No	Time Spend	Sample Size	%
1	Half an hour	108	59
2	Half to one hour	64	32

3	Above one hour	18	9
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

59 % of respondents spend half an hour in college library.

Sample Respondents by Person Help to Settle Problem:

Table 8

S.No	Source of Problem	Sample Size	%
1	Library staff	24	70
2	Chef librarian	4	12
3	Teaching staff	6	18
	Total	34	100

Source: Primary Data

Majority 60% of respondents are satisfied regarding availability of current material.

Sample Respondents by Reading Books Type:

Table 9

S.No	Reading Books Type	Sample Size	%
1	Curriculum orient	36	18
2	General knowledge books	114	57
3	Fictions	24	12
4	Carrier information books	26	13
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

57 % of the sample respondents like to read General knowledge books.

Sample Respondents by Reading Magazines Type:

Table 10

S.No	Reading Magazines Type	Sample Size	%
1	News	90	45
2	Sports	22	11
3	Hobbies	36	18
4	Science	40	20
5	Health	12	6
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

45% of sample respondents like to read News.

Sample Respondents by Reading Type of News:

Table 11

S.No	Type of News	Sample Size	%
1	Local news	72	36
2	National news	68	34
3	Business news	34	17
4	Foreign news	12	6
5	Sports news	14	7
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

36% of sample respondents like to read Local news.

Correlation:

	Facility	Table Chairs	Climate	Attractive	Accessibility	Assistance Provided by Library Staff	Collection
Facility	1						
Table Chairs	0.423031	1					
Climate	0.345841	0.352768	1				
Attractive	0.261549	0.350756	0.320792	1			
Accessibility	0.271487	0.253549	0.21055	0.334859	1		
Assistance Provided by Library Staff	0.102231	0.140491	0.138256	0.32058	0.40562	1	

Collection	0.273203	0.187175	0.237522	0.274625	0.366393	0.79106	1
------------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	---------	---

Source: Primary Data

The result of Karl Pearson's correlation reveals that all variable facility table chairs, climate attractive accessibility assistant providing by library staff. Have positive association at 5% level of significance i.e., assistance providing by library staff has close association with the collection of material.

The main focus of present chapter was to identify the socio economic college library usage of the sample respondent.

- ✓ 67% of the sample respondents are females.
- ✓ Majority 45% of the sample respondents are in the age of 19 years.
- ✓ 31% of the sample respondents are studying B.Com CA.
- ✓ Majority 70% of the sample respondents are able to get orientation class.
- ✓ 91% of the sample respondents are trained by the library staff during orientation class.
- ✓ 55% of the sample respondents are visiting library during free hours.
- ✓ Majority 41% of sample respondents visit library three times per week.
- ✓ 80 percent of sample respondents are studying in colleges which have many sections in college library.

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion:

Findings:

- ✓ 67% are found to be females and the remaining 33% is males.
- ✓ 67% of the sample respondents are females.
- ✓ Majority 45% of the sample respondents are in the age of 19 years.
- ✓ 31% of the sample respondents are studying B.Com CA.
- ✓ Majority 70% of the sample respondents are able to get orientation class.
- ✓ 55% of the sample respondents are visiting library during free hours.
- ✓ A majority 48 % of respondents felt that Reading section considered as a major section. Majority 65 % of respondents are go to two or more sections per visit.
- ✓ 59 % of respondents spend half an hour in college library.
- ✓ 70% of respondents is approach library staff to get grievance.
- ✓ majority 82 % of respondents are have enough time to visit college library.
- ✓ majority 60% of respondents are satisfied regarding availability of current material.
- ✓ 57 % of the sample respondents like to read General knowledge books.
- ✓ 45% of sample respondents like to read News.
- ✓ 36% of sample respondents like to read Local news.
- ✓ 67% of the sample respondents are females.
- ✓ Majority 45% of the sample respondents are in the age of 19 years.
- ✓ 31% of the sample respondents are studying B.Com CA.
- ✓ Majority 70% of the sample respondents are able to get orientation class.
- ✓ 91% of the sample respondents are trained by the library staff during orientation class.
- ✓ 55% of the sample respondents are visiting library during free hours.
- ✓ Majority 41% of sample respondents visit library three times per week.
- ✓ 80 percent of sample respondents are studying in college which have many section in college library

Suggestions:

If library orientation class conducted by the staff with prior notice will leads to increase awareness about library usage among the students. Library orientation class may be supported by Tamil and Malayalam with English will leads to thorough knowledge about the rules. Library staff and teaching staff should motivate to read not only subject books but also general knowledge books. This habit will help to student to get a right job.

Conclusion:

Usage of library materials determines position of each and every student life in a society. If students use the library in properly he will gain and vice versa.

References:

1. Research methodology, N. Thanulingom Himalaya publishing house, Mumbai, Edition 2011, reprint 2013.
2. Research methodology, methods and techniques, second revised edition, C. R. Kothari, new age international publishers Edition 2004, reprint 2013.
3. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled "A Research on Quality Factors Influencing Online Shopping" International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-II, July – 2016. P.No.1-5.